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FOLATE, VITAMIN B₁₂, GLUCOSE ENERGY DEFICIENCY AND NITRIC OXIDE OVERPRODUCTION INHIBITORY EFFECTS ON FIBROSARCOMA IN ADULT HAMSTERS

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We investigated the effect of folate, vitamin B₁₂, glucose energy deficiency and NO overproduction caused by metformin and nitroglycerin on fibrosarcoma in adult hamsters. The 24 Syrian golden hamsters of approximately 100 g, both sexes, were randomly allocated in 3 experimental and 1 control groups of 6 animals in each. 2 x 10⁶ BHK-21/C13 cells in 1 ml were injected subcutaneously on the back of all animals. The first experimental group started peroral treatment with metformin 500 mg/kg daily, second with nitroglycerin 50 mg/kg, and third with combination of metformin 500 mg/kg and nitroglycerin 50 mg/kg, via gastric probe 2 days before tumor inoculation. After 2 weeks, when the tumors were approximately 2 cm in control group, all animals were sacrificed, blood collected for glucose and other analyses, tumors excised, weighed, diameters measured, tumor samples pathohistologically (HE) and immunohistochemically (Ki-67, CD 31, COX IV, GLUT-1, iNOS) assessed and main organs toxicologically analyzed. Tumor volume was determined using the water displacement method and the formula $L \times S^2 / 2$, L - the longest, S - the shortest diameter. Ki-67-positive cells in tumor samples were quantified. Images were taken and processed by imaging software. Statistical significances were determined by the one way ANOVA.

The combination of metformin and nitroglycerin significantly inhibited fibrosarcoma growth in adult hamsters without toxicity.

Administration of metformin with nitroglycerin might be an effective and safe approach in novel nontoxic adjuvant anti-cancer treatment.

Keywords: *Fibrosarcoma, Hamsters, Metformin, Nitroglycerin*

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